

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

STUDIES ON THE PHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF *ARDISIA COLORATA*

Rajib Das, Ashfaqur Rahman, Sukumar Bepary

¹Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

²East West University, Rampura, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

³Jagannath University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 17/10/2018

Available online

31/10/2018

Keywords

Ardisia Colorata,
Analgesic,
Anti-Inflammatory,
Swiss Albino Mice,
Long Evans Rats.

ABSTRACT

Objective: This study was intended to evaluate the phytochemical, analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity of 70% ethanolic extracts of *Ardisia colorata* in swiss albino mice and long evans rats. **Methods:** The ethanolic extract of *A. colorata* stem and leaves were used to determine the presence of phytoconstituents. The analgesic activity of the ethanolic extracts had been carried out by formalin induced hind paw licking responses at a dosage of 250 and 500 mg/kg by mouth (PO) using swiss albino mice. Ketorolac (1 mg/kg, orally), a clinically used analgesic, was used as standard analgesics. The ethanolic extracts were given at a dose of 250 and 500 mg/kg by mouth (PO) for testing their anti-inflammatory activity by carrageenan induced hind paw edema on long evans rats. Diclofenac Sodium (10 mg/kg, orally) was used as standard for anti-inflammatory study. **Results:** The phytochemical screening tests on all extracts showed the presence of a number of pharmacologically important phytochemicals with notably minor traces of flavonoids. The *A. colorata* stem 500 mg/kg dose showed an increase in % pain inhibition in the first phase (36.47%) as well as the late phase (35.09%) in the formalin induced hind paw licking responses of mice. The largest anti-inflammatory activity (13.46%) was shown between 3 and 4 hours by *A. colorata* stem at 250 mg/kg dose when compared to standard. **Conclusions:** The present study indicates that *A. colorata* stem has moderate analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities. The other extract (*A. colorata* leaves) has insignificant analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities.

Corresponding author

Rajib Das

Department of Pharmacy,
Jahangirnagar University,
Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
rajibdas.jupharmacy@gmail.com
+8801684191464

Please cite this article in press as **Rajib Das** et al. *Studies on the Pharmacological Effects of Ardisia Colorata*. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(10).

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Due to producing wide array of bioactive molecules, plants have been a rich source of medicines and evolved as chemical protection against predation or infection. In many developing countries, traditional medicine is one of the primary health care systems [1]. Nearly 50% of drugs used in medicine are of plant origin, and only a small fraction of plants with medicinal activity has been assayed [2]. Therefore, much present research dedicated to the phytochemical investigation of plants which have ethnobotanical information associated with them. The phytochemicals isolated are then screened for different types of biological activity [3].

The plant, *Ardisia colorata* is a tree or shrub from Myrsinaceae family of Genus *Ardisia*. Leaves are alternate or pseudoverticillate, typically punctate or punctate-lineate. Generally the height in its inborn soil, is about 12 feet. The plant was introduced from India, of which it is a native, about the year 1816.

It has been reported that *A. colorata* stem and leaves have antimicrobial effects [4]. Hence, the goal of the current research was to analyze the phytochemical properties and to study the analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects of ethanol extracts of *A. colorata*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Identification and collection of plants

A. colorata was collected from Sylhet, Bangladesh during the month of June-July 2013. We collected the stem and leaves separately. It was then allowed to dry under normal temperature and conditions. The plants were identified by the specialized taxonomists of Bangladesh National Herbarium located at Mirpur, Dhaka (The DAB accession no. for *Ardisia Colorata* is 35589 and the DAB accession no. for *Boehmeria Scabrella* is 35590).

Decontamination, drying, size reduction and storage

The collected plants were washed or gently brushed to remove soil and other debris. Plant material was sliced into small pieces and distributed evenly to aid homogenous drying. The sample was left to dry on trays at ambient temperature and kept in a room with adequate ventilation. The dried samples were allowed to pass through a 1.0mm (20 meshes) screen using the appropriate mill. A 20-mesh sieve is adequate if the sample aliquot to be assayed is greater than 0.5 g. For long-term storage, ground samples were sealed and placed under ambient condition until analyses was completed.

Drugs and chemicals

0.5% formalin was taken from the pharmacology laboratory of Jahangirnagar University. The drugs Ketorolac and Diclofenac Sodium were purchased from Novartis Ltd., Bangladesh and Square Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Bangladesh respectively. Normal Saline (0.9% NaCl) was purchased from Beximco Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Bangladesh. 1% carrageenan solution was purchased from Merck, Germany.

Experimental animals

Swiss albino mice and long evans rats were collected from Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh. All of them were accommodated in standard polypropylene cages and preserved under room temperature of $(24 \pm 2)^{\circ}\text{C}$, relative humidity of 60% - 70%. 48 swiss albino mice of 25g-28g were used to evaluate analgesic activity and 48 long evans rats of 150-250 g were used to evaluate anti-inflammatory activity of *A. colorata* stem and leaves. All the experimental animals were kept for 1 week to acclimatize to the laboratory conditions. All of the experimental processes related to animals were directed in accordance to ethical guidelines of the Faculty of Biological Science, Jahangirnagar University which were also approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Faculty of Biological Science, Jahangirnagar University.

Phytochemical screening

Both primary and secondary metabolites are involved in phytochemical identification. However secondary metabolites are mostly concerned in phytochemical studies. The ethanolic extracts of *A. colorata* was exposed to sequential standard tests for phytochemical identification to find out the presence of amino acids, amines, amides, organic glycosides, alkaloids, flavones, flavonoids, tannins, resins and other phenolic compounds [5].

Biological activities

Analgesic activity

Formalin induced hind paw licking test

Formalin induced hind paw licking test is used to evaluate analgesic property of *A. colorata* stem and leaves [6]. For these, normal saline was used as control. Ketorolac was used as a positive control. To prepare 250 mg/kg test sample, 0.25 gm of stem and leaves of *A. colorata* was taken separately and extracts were dissolved in 10 ml saline water respectively. Similarly, to prepare 500 mg/kg test sample, 0.50 gm of both stem and leaves of *A. colorata* was taken separately and dissolved in 10 ml saline water respectively. Test samples, control and positive control were given orally by means of a feeding needle.

48 swiss albino mice were selected and divided into six groups consisting of eight mice in each group. Each group received a particular treatment i.e. control, positive control and the two doses of the extracts. 0.5% formalin was injected subcutaneously into the right hind paw of the mice. The number of licking responses of the injected paw was taken as an indicator of pain response. Responses were measured for 5 minutes after formalin injection (early phase) and 20–30 minutes after formalin injection (late phase). 70% ethanolic extracts of *A. colorata* stem and leaves (250 and 500 mg/kg, by mouth) were administered 30 minutes before formalin injection to experimental group. On the other hand, Ketorolac (1 mg/kg, by mouth) was administered 30 min before formalin injection to positive control group. Same volume of saline water was given to control group by oral administration.

Anti-inflammatory activity

Carrageenan induced hind paw edema

Carrageenan induced paw swelling or footpad edema, is a convenient method for assessing inflammatory responses to antigenic challenges and irritants [7]. The most convenient, rapid and accurate assessment technique to the rat paw is plethysmometry [8]. A plethysmometer directly measures changes in paw volume by water displacement. For this, 1% carrageenan solution was used as the irritant to induce paw edema. 48 long evans rats were taken and divided into six groups consisting of eight rats in each group. Diclofenac Sodium at 10 mg/kg was administered 1 hour before carrageenan injection.

Normal saline water was given to control group. Diclofenac Sodium was given to positive control group at 10 mg/kg body weight. 70% ethanolic extracts of *A. colorata* stem and leaves at a dose of 250 and 500 mg/kg body weight were given to experimental groups. Half an hour after the oral administration of the test materials, 1% carrageenan was injected to the left hind paw of each animal.

The volume of paw edema was measured at 0.5, 1,2,3,4 and 6 hours using water plethysmometer after administration of carrageenan. The right hind paw served as a reference non-inflamed paw for comparison. The average percent increase in paw volume with time was calculated and compared against the control group. Percent inhibition was calculated using the formula-

$$\% \text{ inhibition formula} = [(V_c - V_t)/V_c] \times 100\%$$

Where, V_c and V_t represent the average edema volume of control and treated animals respectively [9].

RESULTS

Phytochemical screening

Table 1: Phytochemical screening of ethanolic extracts of *A. colorata* stem and leaves.

Phytochemical Constituents	<i>A. colorata</i>	
	Presence (+) / Absence (-)	
	Stem	Leaves
Alkaloid	+	+
Tanins	+++	++
Flavonoids	+	+
Saponins	+++	+++
Gums and Carbohydrates	+++	+++
Reducing Sugar	+++	+++
Steroids	+++	+++
Terpinoids	+++	+++
Glycosides	-	-

Biological activities

Analgesic activity

Formalin induced hind paw licking test

Table 2: Formalin induced hind paw licking responses in mice which indicate the analgesic activity of the ethanolic extracts of *A. colorata* stem and leaves.

	Dose	First Phase (0 – 5 minutes)	Late Phase (20 – 30 minutes)
Control	10% body wt	17.00 ±3.975	11.40 ±3.415
Positive control	1mg/kg	4.60±1.030	10.60 ±3.932
<i>A. colorata</i> stem	250mg/kg	11.60 ±2.502	8.00 ±1.975
	500mg/kg	10.80 ±1.319	7.40 ±1.720
<i>A. colorata</i> leaves	250mg/kg	28.60 ±2.909	19.40 ±7.264
	500mg/kg	13.20 ±1.772	14.00 ±1.923

Figure 1. % inhibition graph of *A. colorata* stem and leaves.

Anti-inflammatory activity

Carrageenan induced hind paw edema.

Table 3: Change in paw volume of different treatments after carrageenan administration in course of time.

	Dose	0 minute	30 minute	1 hour	2 hour	3 hour	4 hour	8 hour
Control	10% body wt	1.216 ±0.067	1.526 ±0.120	1.916 ±0.137	1.852 ±0.219	2.526 ±0.276	2.164 ±0.210	1.544 ±0.157
Positive control	10mg/kg	1.316 ±0.124	1.760 ±0.154	1.848 ±0.186	2.130 ±0.217	2.618 ±0.271	2.352 ±0.284	1.786 ±0.235
<i>A. colorata</i> stem	250mg/kg	1.152 ±0.087	1.642 ±0.193	1.776 ±0.223	2.328 ±0.387	2.186 ±0.205	1.948 ±0.164	1.590 ±0.200
	500mg/kg	1.444 ±0.110	1.682 ±0.049	1.890 ±0.199	2.992 ±0.439	2.628 ±0.364	2.248 ±0.247	1.988 ±0.195
<i>A. colorata</i> leaves	250mg/kg	1.392 ±0.107	1.932 ±0.167	2.058 ±0.131	3.024 ±0.239*	2.480 ±0.200	2.456 ±0.152	1.742 ±0.124
	500mg/kg	1.416 ±0.127	1.772 ±0.143	1.908 ±0.118	3.326 ±0.382*	2.834 ±0.340	2.594 ±0.314	2.204 ±0.234

(Values are Mean ± SEM, n=8; significance at * P<0.05 as compared to the control).

Figure 2. % inhibition of inflammation of *A. colorata* stem.

Figure 3. % inhibition of inflammation of *A. colorata* leaves.

DISCUSSION

The result of the phytochemical investigation of the ethanol extract of *A. colorata* stem and leaves indicate the presence of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, gums and carbohydrates, steroids, terpenoids. Alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins have analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial activities [10-12]. Furthermore, alkaloids have antimalarial, antifungal, cardiotoxic, anticonvulsant activities; flavonoids and saponins have anti-oxidant, anti-viral activities [10-13]. On the other hand, tannins and triterpenoids have anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial and anti-viral activities [14, 15]. Steroidal compounds are important in pharmacy due to their relationship with such compounds those are used as sex hormones and it is thought that steroidal structure could serve as potent starting material in synthesis of these hormones [16].

A. colorata stem and leaves showed analgesic activity in formalin induced hind paw licking responses in swiss albino mice. With 500 mg/kg dose, *Ardisia* stem showed an increase in % of pain inhibition in the first phase (36.47%) as well as the late phase (35.09%) compared to positive control which indicates the moderate analgesic effect. Whereas compared to positive control, *Ardisia* leaves presented a greater % of pain inhibition in the first phase (22.35%), but in the late phase exerted a negative % of pain inhibition (-22.81%) with 500 mg/kg dose which designates lower analgesic effect.

The response of early phase is supposed to represent a direct chemical stimulation of nociceptors due to the irritant effect of formalin on sensory C fibers. It has been found that substance P and bradykinin are formed in the early phase, while histamine, 5-HT, PGs and bradykinin are involved in the late phase [17]. Therefore, we can assume that *A. colorata* stem inhibits substance P, bradykinin, histamine, 5-HT, PGs whereas *A. colorata* leaves inhibits substance P and bradykinin.

By performing carrageenan induced paw swelling test *A. colorata* stem and leaves showed anti-inflammatory activity in long evans mice. For *Ardisia* stem and leaves, the maximum inhibition of edema (13.46%) and (1.82%) respectively, was found to be between 3 and 4 hours in 250 mg/kg dose. Therefore, *Ardisia* stem in 250 mg/kg dose, showed potential anti-inflammatory activity compared to positive control. Furthermore, in 500 mg/kg dose, *Ardisia* stem and leaves, the maximum inhibition of edema (1.38%) and (0.42%) respectively, were found to be between 1 and 2 hours.

Since this experimental model did not confirm which alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tanins, triterpenoids were responsible for analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities, therefore, some bioactivity guided isolations of compounds from this plant are required.

CONCLUSION

The present study indicated that the ethanol extracts of the *A. colorata* leaves has insignificant analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects. However, *A. colorata* stem has moderate analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects. It may be proposed that more study should be carried out using higher doses of the extracts concerned. If possible, other potential pharmacological activities are explored (anti-cancer, antipsychotic etc). Since natural products are so diverse and present distinct physicochemical properties (e.g. solubility); other solvents can be used for extraction of pharmacological constituents from this plant.

Financial Support

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial or not-for-profit sectors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We express utmost sincere gratefulness to Md. Abdul Awoal, Department of Pharmacy, Jahangirnagar University, for providing constant support and technical skills to accomplish this work. We also grateful to Pharmacology Lab, Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh for their lab facilities and technical supports.

Competing interest

We announce that we have no conflict of interest.

Ethical matter

The set of rules followed for animal experiment were approved by the institutional animal ethical committee.

REFERENCES

1. Weleni DL. Antimicrobial activities of Medicinal Plants: A Review. IJATIR. 2017; 9(7): 1198-1202.
2. Veeresham C. Natural products derived from plants as a source of drugs. J Adv Pharm Technol Res. 2012; 3(4): 200–201.
3. Harborne, J.B. A Guide to Modern Techniques of Plant Analysis. 5th Edition. Chapman and Hall Ltd, London, 1998.
4. Syed E, Mashroor B, Hossain FMD, Bi-Illah N, Bhattacharjee R, Hannan JMA. Evaluation of phytochemical screening and antimicrobial activities of ethanolic extracts of leaves and bark of *Ardisia colorata*. Int. j. pharm. life sci. 2013;2(4): 1-7.
5. Chowdhury S, Poddar SK, Zaheen S, Noor FA, Haque S, Sukul A, Sunjida SB, Mazumder MU, Ahmed N, Akbar N. Phytochemical screening and evaluation of cytotoxic and hypoglycemic properties of *Mangifera indica* peels. Asian Pac J Trop Biomed. 2016;7(1): 1-4.
6. Dubuisson D, Dennis SG. The formalin test: a quantitative study of the analgesic effects of morphine, meperidine, and brain stem stimulation in rats and cats. North-Holland Biomedical Press. 1977;4(1977): 161-174.
7. Fehrenbacher JC, Vasko MR, Duarte DB. Models of Inflammation: Carrageenan- or Complete Freund's Adjuvant-Induced Edema and Hypersensitivity in the Rat. Curr Protoc Pharmacol. 2012; 70:5.4: 1-9.
8. Fereidoni M, Ahmadiani A, Semnani S, Javan M. An accurate and simple method for measurement of paw edema. J Pharmacol Toxicol Methods. 2000;43: 11-14.
9. Yu Su J, Chan Li Q, Zhu L. Evaluation of the in vivo anti-inflammatory activity of a flavone glycoside from *Cancrinia discoidea* (ledeb.) Poljak. EXCLI J. 2011;10:110-116.
10. Kaur R, Arora S. Alkaloids-important therapeutic secondary metabolites of plant origin. A review. J Crit Rev. 2015;2(3): 1-8.
11. Kumar S, Pandey AK. Chemistry and biological activities of flavonoids. A review. Sci. World J. 2013;2013.
12. Barbosa ADP. An overview on the biological and pharmacological activities of saponins. A review. Int J Pharm Pharm Sci. 2014;6(8): 47-50.
13. Desai SD, Desai DG, Kaur H. Saponins and their Biological Activities. A review. Pharma Times. 2009;41(3): 2-5.
14. M. K, S. J. Tannins: An antinutrient with positive effect to manage Diabetes. P review. Res.J.Recent Sci. 2012;1(12): 1-8.
15. Berhardt LV. Triterpenoids: Synthesis, Uses in Cancer Treatment and other Biological Activities. New York: Nova Science Publishers, Inc.; 2017.
16. Edeoga HO, Okwu DE, Mbaebie BO. Phytochemical constituents of some Nigerian medicinal plants. Afr. J. Biotechnol. 2005;4(7): 685-688.
17. Florentino IF, Nascimento MVM, Galdino PM, Brito AFD, Rocha FFD, Tonussi CR, et al. Evaluation of analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities of *Hydrocotyle umbellata* L., Araliaceae (acariçoba) in mice. An Acad Bras Cienc. 2013;85(3): 987-997.

54878478451181010

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

